

HYBRID COOLING AND WASTE-HEAT RECOVERY SYSTEM FOR SOLAR PV PANELS

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Abstract— This paper presents a hybrid PV cooling and waste-heat recovery system using aluminium fins, DC fans, a water sprayer and TEG modules. A 390 W monocrystalline PV panel was tested in Rajshahi, Bangladesh. The system increased efficiency from 17% to 22%, raised average power from 233.70 W to 295.42 W and reduced panel temperature by 24.8°C. It also produced 0.66088 kWh/day net excess energy with a payback period of 4.76 years. The results confirm that integrated cooling, cleaning and waste-heat recovery can improve PV performance.

Keywords— photovoltaic panel, hybrid cooling, thermoelectric generator, waste-heat recovery, water sprayer.

I. INTRODUCTION

PV modules lose efficiency when absorbed solar energy is converted into heat instead of electricity. In hot climates, this temperature rise becomes more critical, while dust accumulation on the front glass further reduces light transmission and daily energy output [1].

Existing studies and earlier experimental work show that fins, DC fans, water spraying and TEG modules can support PV cooling, cleaning and waste-heat recovery [2]. This study extends that approach by testing these components together as a compact hybrid system under outdoor conditions in Rajshahi, Bangladesh.

II. METHODOLOGY

The system used a 390 W monocrystalline PV panel with aluminium fins, DC fans, a water sprayer and two TEG modules.

A. Experimental Setup

Rear-side fins and four 12 V DC fans were used for heat removal. A front-side PVC sprayer provided cooling and dust cleaning, while two 12 W TEG modules recovered waste heat.

B. Performance Measurement

Uncooled and hybrid conditions were compared by measuring irradiance, temperature, voltage, current, airflow and water flow. Efficiency, power output, auxiliary energy use, TEG output and economic benefit were evaluated.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The hybrid system improved PV performance through cooling, dust removal and waste-heat recovery. Water spraying cooled and cleaned the panel, while fins, DC fans and TEG modules enhanced heat dissipation and energy recovery.

PV efficiency increased from 17% to 22%, average power rose from 233.70 W to 295.42 W, and panel temperature decreased by 24.8°C. These results support the reviewer-noted temperature reduction and efficiency improvement. Table 1 summarizes the main performance comparison.

Table 1. Performance summary of the hybrid PV cooling system.

Parameter	Without cooling	Hybrid system	Effect
PV efficiency	17%	22%	+5 points
Avg. PV power	233.70 W	295.42 W	+61.72 W
Daily net gain	-	0.66088 kWh	after auxiliaries
Lifetime saving	-	36,745 BDT	20 years
Payback period	-	4.76 years	≈ 4 y 9 m

Figure 1. Experimental comparison of average PV power and efficiency.

Figure 1 shows improved average PV power and efficiency after applying the hybrid cooling system. The techno-economic analysis also shows 0.66088 kWh/day net excess energy, 36,745 BDT net saving, and a 4.76-year payback period.

IV. CONCLUSION

The hybrid PV system improved efficiency from 17% to 22%, raised average power from 233.70 W to 295.42 W and reduced panel temperature by 24.8°C. It also produced 0.66088 kWh/day net excess energy with a 4.76-year payback period. Future work should focus on long-term testing, automated spray control and better TEG performance.

References

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